

Practitioner-oriented consulting on agroforestry systems in Austria

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In total 5.6% of agricultural land in Austria is in agroforestry use, grazing in orchards being the main agroforestry system, and silvoarable agroforestry systems creating a small share of agroforestry. Despite agroforestry being practiced, no general advisory services on agroforestry have existed in Austria. EIP-Agri Operational Group “Agroforestry in Austria” addressed the need for agroforestry advisory services through creating practitioner-oriented consulting for agroforestry systems in Austria.

Photo 1. A newly established agroforestry system with walnut trees and strawberry in Austria (FiBL, T. Markut).

Need for agroforestry advisory as the background for the project

Farms interested in agroforestry have implemented agroforestry without advisory support as no general advisory services on agroforestry have existed in Austria. EIP-Agri Operational Group “Agroforestry in Austria” addressed the need for agroforestry advisory services through creating practitioner-oriented consulting for agroforestry systems in Austria. This was done through seeking solutions and aiming to leverage the pioneering work of the model farms in for other interested farms in the region.

The aims of the “Agroforestry in Austria” project were 1) formation of a network on agroforestry, 2) know-how transfer on agroforestry to Austria with special consideration of the findings of the international EIP-Agri Focus Group Agroforestry, 3) identification of suitable agroforestry systems for different locations and farm orientations in eastern Austria, 4) concrete planning and implementation of agroforestry systems on six project farms (agroforestry model farms), 5) documentation of implementation steps, practical successes and challenges, as well as decision-making processes, 6) creation of information materials tailored to the target group of stakeholders interested in agroforestry, and 7) dissemination of the project results and agroforestry knowledge among farmers, (organic) farming advisors and other actors in the agricultural sector.

EIP-Agri Operational Group “Agroforestry in Austria” had a budget of 228642.85 euros for the project duration from October 2019 to September 2022. Research Institute of Organic Agriculture FiBL coordinated the project with partners being six Austrian agricultural holdings interested in agroforestry (model farms), Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW), Consulting & Design Burkhard Kayser, Grottenhof/Hardt Technical College and Hatzendorf Plant Cultivation Experimental Station, Institute of Organic Agriculture and Department of Viticulture and Fruit Growing &

Institute of Organic Farming at University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), organic farming association Bio-Austria in Lower Austria, and Lower Austria Chamber of Agriculture. Other partners for agroforestry promotion, dissemination and education included agroforestry association ARGE Agroforst and Rural Training Institute Ländliches Fortbildungsinstitut Österreich.

Photo 2. A field visit of the “Agroforestry in Austria” stakeholders at an agroforestry farm in Switzerland (FiBL, T. Markut).

Implementation of agroforestry model farms

Agroforestry systems were planned and implemented as site-adapted systems on six model farms in the states of Lower Austria and Upper Austria in Austria. The agroforestry systems implemented on the model farms mainly aimed at wind protection, biodiversity promotion, microclimate improvement, landscape enhancement, erosion protection, preservation of old fruit varieties, and fruit and nut production. The model farms purchased the tree seedlings used in the agroforestry systems with their own resources as EIP-Agri does not provide investment funding. “Agroforestry in Austria” project supported planning and implementation of the demonstration sites. With support from project partners and German and Swiss consultants, suitable site-adapted agroforestry systems were identified, planting plans designed, and support for farmers for maintaining the systems was established.

The implemented model farms were:

- The organic farm Erasim-Labuda, Rabensburg, Lower Austria. The agroforestry system was established on cleared arable land with aims to increase biodiversity, slow winds, and produce valuable fruit. In autumn 2020, two rows of chestnut, pecan, Turkish hazel, almond, and papavi were planted on the farm. The farm website: <https://erla-exoten.at/de/>
- The organic farm Weinbub, Windpassing, Lower Austria. The agroforestry system consists of three rows of walnut trees, from which the nut and in future also valuable timber will be harvested. The agroforestry system also provide shading for the strawberry crop, slows wind speed, and enhances agricultural landscape. The first rows of trees were planted in autumn 2020 and they were expected to be expanded later. The farm website: <https://www.beerenhunger.at/>
- The organic farm Grand, Absdorf, Lower Austria. The farm is a research and demonstration farm where different national and international research projects are being implemented. The focus of the farm is on soil health, agroforestry and market gardening. The agroforestry system implemented on the farm is a multi-purpose hedgerow of trees with 32 old fruit varieties. The implemented agroforestry system aims at wind protection and biodiversity promotion. The farm website: <https://grandfarm.at/>
- An organic farm in Lower Austria. The agroforestry tree rows planted on the farm are intended to increase biodiversity in the landscape and bring more trees back to the region. The tree rows also divide larger areas in smaller plots. The agroforestry system produces valuable timber and fruits which could also be used to produce fine spirits.
- The organic farm Hager, Ried in der Riedmark, Upper Austria. The agroforestry tree rows of trees planted at the farm include walnut, linden, Turkish hazel, elm, sycamore, Norway maple, wild service tree, cherry, oak, and chestnut. The agroforestry system enhances the landscape, positively

influences microclimate and water balance, and provides shade and protection for turkeys and cattle. The farm website: <https://www.biohofhager.at/>

- An organic farm, Greater Linz area, Upper Austria. The agroforestry system was established to control soil erosion as a part of the farmland is located on a slope. A key-line agroforestry system with planting tree rows along contour lines is used to direct surface water in a targeted manner. The planted trees include fruit trees, different nut species, oak, service tree, wild service tree, alder, Turkish hazel and poplar.

These model farms are used as demonstration sites and practical knowledge generation sites in the practitioner-oriented consulting on agroforestry within the “Agroforestry in Austria” project. Practitioners’ interest in agroforestry facilitated establishing the agroforestry demonstration sites. The model farms will continue to be used as agroforestry demonstration sites for the practitioners interested in implementing agroforestry also after completion of the “Agroforestry in Austria” project.

Besides implementing the agroforestry model farms, a guiding document for consulting and advisory (Meindl & Markut, 2023) was produced in the “Agroforestry in Austria” project. The document is published in the local language, German. It describes agroforestry, describes how farms and environment can benefit from agroforestry, provides tools for planning and implementing agroforestry systems at farm level, provides a list of suitable species in Austria, and gives solutions for challenges possibly faced in agroforestry systems.

Lessons learned and future activities

The EIP-Agri Operational Group “Agroforestry in Austria” created a novel consulting service on agroforestry for Austrian agriculture for guidance, support and learning possibilities on agroforestry.

Photo 3. Young agroforestry plantation with rowan, horse chestnut, and wild cherry for timber production and fruit for birds and humans, Lower Austria, Austria (FiBL, T. Markut).

The project raised awareness on agroforestry among different stakeholders such as farmers and advisors, showcased concretely implementation of different agroforestry systems in practice through model farms, and informed about the potential benefits these systems deliver.

“Agroforestry in Austria” project also contributed to establishment of spin-off projects. One of the spin-off projects of “Agroforestry in Austria” project is Agroforestry Education Initiative in 2023-2024. This project aimed at providing farms interested in agroforestry with information on agroforestry implementation through for instance visits to best practice farms, agroforestry information exchange meetings, seminars on agroforestry management, and agroforestry dissemination material production.

About FOREST4EU project

The article has been produced in FOREST4EU project as a part of capacity building materials directed to stakeholders across Europe. Whereas innovations developed in the operational groups are typically available locally, FOREST4EU project aims at transferring knowledge and best practices on forestry and agroforestry to stakeholders and operational groups across Europe.

Photo 4. A 3-year-old agroforestry system for slope stabilization and habitat creation based on a key-line system in the state of Upper Austria in Austria (FiBL, T. Markut).

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Further information

[Visit the project page: “Agroforestry in Austria” network](#)

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